

Pulmonary Function Abnormalities in Patients of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus**Deepak Gupta¹, Kumar Chitresh^{2*}, Setia Mansi³, Verma Suchita⁴, Rijhwani Puneet⁵, Parakh Rishabh⁶, Shah Sarthak⁷, Kalra Vidita⁸, Tyagi Ambika⁹**¹Professor, Dept. of General Medicine, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur^{2,3,4,6,7,8} Resident, Dept. of General Medicine, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur⁵Professor and Head of Department, Dept. of General Medicine, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur⁹Assistant Professor, Dept. of General Medicine, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Long duration elevation of blood sugar can lead to damage to blood vessels, kidneys, retina, nerves etc. It may damage pulmonary vasculature and via inflammatory mediators reduce the lung function. So this study tries to find out relationship between diabetes and lung function.**Material and Methods:** A Hospital based observational descriptive study with cross - sectional design was done among patient with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus attending OPD and being admitted in the Department of General Medicine, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur during the period of study. Detail history was taken, BMI was noted, diabetic parameters were investigated and spirometry was done to note the PFT values.**Results:** The increase in BMI lead to significant decrease in lung function ($p < 0.05$). Poor diabetic control (increase in HbA1c) and increase in duration of diabetes is significantly negatively correlated to FVC, FEV1 and TLC ($p < 0.05$). Even PPBS is significantly negatively correlated to FVC and FEV1 ($p < 0.05$)**Conclusion:** Increase in blood sugar level and poor control along with increase in BMI significantly reduce lung function. Hence strict control of blood sugar level is essential to halt the progress of decline in lung function in type2 diabetes patients.**Keywords:** Spirometry, BMI, Lung Function, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus.

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Introduction

Diabetes is a disease which present with elevated blood sugar level. Long duration elevation of blood sugar can lead to damage to blood vessels, kidneys, retina, nerves etc. As per literature around the world about 422 million people are suffering from diabetes. Majority of these are from low and middle income countries. [1] Effect of long term hyperglycemia in diabetes causes atherosclerotic changes in vascular endothelium which leads to stiffening and decrease supply distal to the vessel by a complex mechanism. [2,3] In diabetes there is more respiratory symptoms compared to those without diabetes and a correlation between diabetes and occurrence with diseases like asthma, COPD etc is suspected by specialist.[4] The alveolar-capillary network in the lung is a large micro vascular unit and may be affected by micro-angiopathy. The pathologic effect of diabetes on many organs are widely studied but the effect of diabetes on lung tissue and function are not widely studied. So this study was done with objectives:-

- To evaluate the pulmonary functions abnormalities in type 2 diabetic patients.
- To find the association between lung function and diabetes.

Materials and Methods

A Hospital based observational descriptive study with cross - sectional design was done among patient with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus attending OPD and being admitted in the Department of General Medicine, Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Hospital Jaipur during the period of study. Due ethical clearance was taken from institutional ethical committee. Patients earlier diagnosed with T2DM according to American Diabetic Association were enrolled [5]. Detail history was taken regarding socio-demographic characteristics, any chronic disease, duration of diabetes etc. Blood investigations were done to measure the blood glucose level both fasting and post prandial and also HbA1C was measured. Then

spirometry was done to measure the lung function and it was compared with normal or predicted.

Data compiled in MS Excel and analysis was done in SPSS version 16 and results were described using Chi square test and considered significant if p value found to be less than 0.05.

Results

In this study most of the study subject i.e 53% (53) belonged to age group 51-60 yrs followed by 41-50yrs (35%), 31-40yrs (8%) and 61-70yrs (4%) respectively. The mean age was 50.94 yrs (SD 6.34). 59% (59) of the study subjects were male and rest 41% (41) were females with male to female ratio is 1.43:1.

According to BMI most of the study subjects i.e 45% (45) were pre obese (25-29.9 Kg/Sqm), 37% (37) were of normal BMI (18.5-24.9) and 18% (18) were obese (BMI 30 and above). The lab blood sugar characteristics of the study subject showed that mean FBS and PPBS were 138.78 mg/dl (SD 37.55) and 211.93 (SD 63.81) respectively. The mean HbA1c was 7.8% (SD 1.14). Most of the study subject i.e 46% (46) had HbA1c level from

7.1-9%, 37% (37) had HbA1c < 7% and rest 17%(17) had HBA1c >9%.

Pulmonary function test values (PFT) of the study subjects were calculated. The mean Forced vital capacity (FVC) was 2.97 (SD 0.73) litres, Forced Expiratory volume in 1 second (FEV1) was 2.33 (SD 0.66), total lung capacity (TLC) was 3.84 (SD 0.74) liters and FEV1/FVC ratio was 78.21% (SD 8.53). Mean of calculated PFT values in terms of % of predicted values which comes out to be FVC 74.07% (SD 18.22), FEV1 72.31% (SD 17.69) and TLC 73.73 (SD 11.81).

On comparison of PFT values between male and females it was found that mean of FVC in male and female was 3.23 (SD 0.72) and 2.59 (SD 0.55) liters respectively. Similarly the mean of FEV1 in male and female is 2.60 (SD 0.66) and 1.94 (SD 0.41) liters respectively. Again the mean of TLC in male and female is 4.22 (SD 0.63) and 3.29 (SD 0.50) liters respectively. All these differences were statistically significant (p=0.000). Similarly the mean of FEV1/FVC in male and female was 79% (SD 10) and 75% (SD 3) respectively and this difference was also statistically significant (p=0.024)

Table 1: Mean PFT according to BMI and Duration of diabetes (N=100)

Mean PFT Vs BMI	BMI (Kg/sqm)			p
	Normal BMI (n=37)	Pre-Obese (n=45)	Obese (n=18)	
FVC (Litres)	3.28(0.81)	2.91(0.67)	2.47(0.22)	0.000
FEV1 (Litres)	2.69(0.73)	2.23(0.56)	1.83(0.13)	0.000
TLC (Litres)	4.40(0.65)	3.62(0.63)	3.26(0.30)	0.000
FEV1/FVC (%)	80.01(8.37)	78.35(9.68)	74.14 (2.89)	0.055
Mean PFT Vs Duration of Diabetes	Duration Of Diabetes (yrs)			p
	<5 (n=20)	6-10 (n=65)	>10 (n=15)	
FVC (Litres)	3.81 (0.70)	2.83(0.60)	2.45(0.21)	0.000
FEV1 (Litres)	3.12(0.52)	2.20(0.56)	1.84(0.16)	0.000
TLC (Litres)	4.59(0.62)	3.74(0.65)	3.29(0.51)	0.000
FEV1/FVC (%)	81.12(7.85)	78.28(9.31)	74.01(1.98)	0.055

On comparing mean FVC with basal metabolic index (BMI) it was found that mean FVC with BMI (normal BMI, pre obese and obese) varied from 3.28 (SD 0.81), 2.91 (SD 0.67) and 2.47 (SD 0.22) liters respectively (p=0.000). Similarly on comparing mean FEV1 with basal metabolic index (BMI) it was found that mean FEV1 with BMI (normal BMI, pre obese and obese) varied from 2.69 (SD 0.73), 2.23 (SD 0.56) and 1.83 (SD 0.13) liters respectively (p=0.000). Again on comparing mean TLC with basal metabolic index (BMI) it was found that mean TLC with BMI varied from 4.40 (SD 0.65), 3.62 (SD 0.63) and 3.26 (SD 0.30) liters respectively. (p=0.000).

This means all three PFT values FVC, FEV1 and TLC decreases significantly with increase in

BMI.(p<0.001) Finally on comparing mean FEV1/FVC with BMI it was found that mean FEV1/FVC with BMI varied from 80.01 (SD 8.37), 78.35 (SD 09.68) and 74.14 (SD 02.89) liters respectively. It means FEV1/FVC decreases with increase in BMI though not significant (p>0.05).

On comparing mean PFT values with duration of diabetes it was found that mean FVC varied with duration of diabetes ≤ 5 years, 6-10yrs and > 10 years from 3.81 (SD 0.70), 2.83 (SD 0.60) and 2.45 (SD 0.21) liters respectively; mean FEV1 varied from 3.12 (SD 0.52), 2.20 (SD 0.56) and 1.84 (SD 0.16) liters respectively and mean TLC varied from 4.59 (SD 0.62), 3.74 (SD 0.65) and 3.29 (SD 0.51) liters respectively and this difference (decrease) in FVC, FEV1 and TLC with duration of diabetes was

statistically significant ($p=0.000$). In figure 1 means plot between mean of TLC and duration of diabetes showing negative linear relationship.

On comparing mean FEV1/FVC with duration of diabetes it was found that mean FEV1/FVC with

duration of diabetes ≤ 5 years, 6-10yrs and > 10 years varied from 81.12 (SD 7.85), 78.28 (SD 09.31) and 74.01 (SD 01.98) liters respectively and this difference in FEV1/FVC with duration of diabetes was not statistically significant ($p>0.05$).

Figure 1: Means plot between TLC and duration of Diabetes

Table 2: Correlation between PFT values and diabetic parameters

PFT Vs Diabetic parameters	FVC		FEV1		FEV1/FVC		TLC	
	r	p	r	p	r	p	r	p
FBS	-0.166	0.098	-0.176	0.080	-0.075	0.460	-0.185	0.065
PPBS	-0.239	0.017	-0.234	0.019	-0.078	0.442	-0.182	0.069
HbA1C	-0.280	0.005	-0.251	0.012	-0.094	0.350	-0.261	0.009
Duration of Diabetes	-0.533	0.000	-0.573	0.000	-0.166	0.099	-0.546	0.000

On doing the correlation analysis between PFT values and various diabetic parameters as shown in table 2 it was found that the FVC, FEV1, FEV1/FVC and TLC were though negatively correlated but were not significantly correlated with fasting blood sugar (FBS) with p values >0.05 . But the correlation analysis shows FVC and FEV1 were significantly negatively correlated with post prandial blood sugar (PPBS) with p value <0.05 . In

the similar manner FVC, FEV1 and TLC were significantly negatively correlated with control i.e HbA1c with p values <0.05 . In the similar manner FVC, FEV1 and TLC were significantly negatively correlated with duration of diabetes with p values <0.001 . Scatter plot showing association between PPBS, HbA1C and duration of diabetes and PFT values as in figure 2,3 and 4 showing the negative linear relationship.

Figure 2: Scatter Plot Showing Correlation between FEV1 and PPBS

Figure 3: Scatter Plot Showing Correlation between FEV1 and HbA1c

Figure 4: Scatter Plot showing Correlation between FEV1 and Duration of Diabetes

Discussion

Chronic diseases of chronic respiratory system is the third most common cause of death globally.[6] The primary risk factors for COPD were found to be air pollution, tobacco smoking, and occupational hazards. [7] Similarly the prevalence of diabetes is being increasing. An estimated 2 million people died in 2019 from diabetes and renal damage brought on by the condition. [8]

The body's chronic underlying inflammation is a co-factor in diabetes. Lungs may also be impacted by this. Diabetes increases the likelihood of respiratory symptoms in people of the same age without the disease. The relationship between diabetes and lung cancer, pulmonary fibrosis, dyspnea, asthma, and COPD has been demonstrated or is being conjectured. Diabetes increases oxidative stress, which can result in complex lung tissue issues. [9] This study tries to find out pulmonary functions abnormalities in type 2 diabetic patients to present the association between lung function and diabetes.

In this study most of the study subject i.e 53% (53) belonged to age group 51-60 yrs followed by 41-50yrs (35%), 31-40yrs (8%) and 61-70yrs (4%) respectively. The mean age was 50.94 yrs (SD 6.34). 59% (59) of the study subjects were male

and rest 41% (41) were females with male to female ratio is 1.43:1.

Pulmonary function test values (PFT) of the study subjects were calculated. The mean Forced vital capacity (FVC) was 2.97 (SD 0.73) litres, Forced Expiratory volume in 1 second (FEV1) was 2.33 (SD 0.66), total lung capacity (TLC) was 3.84 (SD 0.74) liters and FEV1/FVC ratio was 78.21% (SD 8.53). Mean of calculated PFT values in terms of % of predicted values which comes out to be FVC 74.07% (SD 18.22), FEV1 72.31% (SD 17.69) and TLC 73.73 (SD 11.81).

PFT values in relation to Diabetic Parameters

The lab blood sugar characteristics of the study subject showed that mean FBS and PPBS were 138.78 mg/dl (SD 37.55) and 211.93 (SD 63.81) respectively. The mean HbA1c was 7.8% (SD 1.14). Most of the study subject i.e 46% (46) had HbA1c level from 7.1-9%, 37% (37) had HbA1c < 7% and rest 17% (17) had HbA1c >9%.

On doing the correlation analysis between PFT values and various diabetic parameters it was found that the FVC, FEV1, FEV1/FVC and TLC were though negatively correlated but were not significantly correlated with fasting blood sugar (FBS) with p values >0.05. But the correlation analysis shows FVC and FEV1 were significantly

negatively correlated with post prandial blood sugar (PPBS) with p value <0.05 . In the similar manner FVC, FEV₁ and TLC were significantly negatively correlated with control i.e HbA1c with p values <0.05 . In the similar manner FVC, FEV₁ and TLC were significantly negatively correlated with duration of diabetes with p values <0.001 .

Ashish Sharma et al [10] in 2023 in a hospital based study, studied the spirometric lung function in type 2 diabetes mellitus and found that 32% of patients had good glycemic control whereas 68% of patients had poor glycemic control with mean level of HbA1C was 8.8 with an SD of 2.4. The majority of patients had an HbA1C level between 7-10% (48%); 20% of patients had an HbA1C level $>10\%$. This finding is similar to our study {46% (46) belonged to HbA1c level 7.1-9% and 17% >9 HbA1c}. Sharma et al found a significant difference (decrease) in all the spirometric measures among cases. The average difference was 13.54%. FEF₂₅₋₇₅ showed the highest difference followed by PEFR, FVC, FEV₁, and FEV₁ %. In our study too FVC and FEV₁ is significantly negatively correlated (negative r value) with post prandial fasting blood sugar (PPBS) with p values <0.05 . Glycemic control or (HbA1C) was significantly correlated with FEF₂₅₋₇₅, PEFR, FEV₁, FVC, and FEV₁ % in descending order in the study by Sharma et al. Glycemic control correlated comparatively more strongly with all spirometric parameters than the duration of diabetes. In our study too FVC, FEV₁ and TLC are significantly negatively correlated (negative r value) with control i.e HbA1c with p values <0.05 .

Shah et al [11] in 2013 studied the PFT in T2DM patients in Diabetes outpatient Department of Sassoon General Hospitals in 60 diabetic and 60 normal controls and found that all the pulmonary parameters, that is, FVC, FEV₁, FEF₂₅, FEF₅₀, FEF₇₅, FEF₂₅₋₇₅, FEF_{0.2-1.2}, and PEFR were significantly reduced except FEV₁/FVC in patients of type 2 DM as compared with the healthy controls ($P < 0.05$). The ratio FEV₁/FVC is almost equal in normal controls and diabetic patients ($P > 0.05$). Mean HbA1c was mean 7.12 ± 1.36 and it was not significantly correlated with FVC and FEV₁. But in our study HbA1c is significantly negatively correlated with FVC and FEV₁ ($p < 0.05$).

Similar to our study findings systemic review between lung function and type 2 DM by Klein et al [12] in 2010 showed that adults with diabetes mellitus have lower forced vital capacity (FVC) and forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV₁). The reduced lung function in patients with diabetes is inversely related to blood glucose levels.

The Atherosclerosis Risk in Communities (ARIC) Study by Yeh et al [13] in 2008 found adults with

diabetes also had significantly lower FVC, FEV₁, FVC (% predicted), and FEV₁ (% predicted) at baseline compared to adults without diabetes. In our study too FVC, FEV₁ and TLC were significantly negatively correlated with HbA1c. In contrast, the ratio of FEV₁ to FVC was significantly higher in adults with diabetes than without diabetes. In our study we did not find any relationship of diabetes with FEV₁/FVC ratio. In diabetic adults, higher fasting glucose was significantly associated with further reductions in FVC and FVC (% predicted) and FEV₁ (all p for trend < 0.001). But we did not find significant relationship between fasting glucose and PFT values though PFT values decrease with increase in fasting blood sugar level. Relationships between poor glycemic control (as indicated by higher % HbA1c) and reduced FVC and FEV₁ were significant and graded. This finding is similar to our study.

So over all in most of the studies, the FVC, FEV₁, FEV₁/FVC and TLC decrease with higher level of glycemia compared to non diabetic subject which is similar to our finding. Even those with poor glycemic control in long run as depicted by HbA1c level most of the studies showed a decline in PFT values and that finding is also similar to the finding in this study.

Effect of duration of Diabetes on PFT values.

On comparing mean PFT values with duration of diabetes it was found that mean FVC varied with duration of diabetes ≤ 5 years, 6-10yrs and > 10 years from 3.81 (SD 0.70), 2.83 (SD 0.60) and 2.45 (SD 0.21) liters respectively; mean FEV₁ varied from 3.12 (SD 0.52), 2.20 (SD 0.56) and 1.84 (SD 0.16) liters respectively and mean TLC varied from 4.59 (SD 0.62), 3.74 (SD 0.65) and 3.29 (SD 0.51) liters respectively and this difference (decrease) in FVC, FEV₁ and TLC with duration of diabetes was statistically significant ($p=0.000$).

On comparing mean FEV₁/FVC with duration of diabetes it was found that mean FEV₁/FVC with duration of diabetes ≤ 5 years, 6-10yrs and > 10 years varied from 81.12 (SD 7.85), 78.28 (SD 09.31) and 74.01 (SD 01.98) liters respectively and this difference in FEV₁/FVC with duration of diabetes was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Various studies showed the effect of duration of diabetes in PFT values in diabetic patients. Sharma et al [10] in 2023 found duration of diabetes to be significantly correlated with FEF₂₅₋₇₅, FEV₁, PEFR, and FVC in descending order. However, it was not significantly correlated with FEV₁%. Shah et al [11] in 2013 found mean duration of diabetes among cases to be 6.56 ± 5.86 yrs but it bears no significant correlation with FVC and FEV₁. Yeh et al [13] in 2008 in their study found that compared to their non-diabetes counterparts, diabetic adults

who reported longer duration of diabetes had further reductions in FVC, FEV₁, FVC (% predicted), and FEV₁ (% predicted) (all p for trend <0.0001). This finding is similar to our study as with increased duration of diabetes the PFT values are decreasing.

Similar to our study Systemic review by Klein et al [12] in 2010 showed that the reduced lung function in patients with diabetes is inversely related duration of diabetes and its severity and is independent of smoking or obesity.

Effect of BMI on PFT values in T2DM patients

In our study BMI most of the study subjects i.e 45% (45) were of pre obese (25-29.9 Kg/Sqm) range, 37% (37) were of normal BMI (18.5-24.9) and 18% (18) were of obese reange (BMI 30 and above) On comparing mean FVC with basal metabolic index (BMI) it was found that mean FVC with BMI (normal BMI, pre obese and obese) varied from 3.28 (SD 0.81), 2.91 (SD 0.67) and 2.47 (SD 0.22) liters respectively (p=0.000). Similarly on comparing mean FEV₁ with basal metabolic index (BMI) it was found that mean FEV₁ with BMI (normal BMI, pre obese and obese) varied from 2.69 (SD 0.73), 2.23 (SD 0.56) and 1.83 (SD 0.13) liters respectively (p=0.000). Again on comparing mean TLC with basal metabolic index (BMI) it was found that mean TLC with BMI varied from 4.40 (SD 0.65), 3.62 (SD 0.63) and 3.26 (SD 0.30) liters respectively. (p=0.000).

This means all three PFT values FVC , FEV₁ and TLC decreases significantly with increase in BMI.(p<0.001) Finally on comparing mean FEV₁/FVC with BMI it was found that mean FEV₁/FVC with BMI varied from 80.01 (SD 8.37), 78.35 (SD 09.68) and 74.14 (SD 02.89) liters respectively. It means FEV₁/FVC decreases with increase in BMI though not significant (p>0.05).

Similar studies were done to see the effect of BMI on PFT in diabetic subjects. Shah et al in 2013 in a similar study found that age, height, and weight of both the groups were comparable as statistically there was no difference between them (P > 0.05). Borst et al [14] in 2010 in his metanalysis found that the meta regression analyses for FEV₁, FVC, FEV₁/ FVC, and DLCO, respectively, showed no significance for diabetic BMI (P 5 .16, P 5 .40, P 5 .62, P 5 .54) or HbA1c (P 5 .99, P 5 .19, P 5 .79, P 5 .23), indicating that heterogeneity could not be explained by any of these variables. P Lange et al [15] in 2002 showed low BMI (only with regard to FEV₁ decline) was significantly associated with increased decline of lung function. So in our study obese has decreased PFT values compared to normal BMI which is in contract to other studies. Since BMI has an independent effect on PFT

values so regression analysis need to be done to get a true idea.

Effect of gender on PFT values in Diabetes

On comparison of PFT values between male and females it was found that mean of FVC in male and female was 3.23 (SD 0.72) and 2.59 (SD 0.55)liters respectively. Similarly the mean of FEV₁ in male and female is 2.60 (SD 0.66) and 1.94 (SD 0.41) liters respectively. Again the mean of TLC in male and female is 4.22 (SD 0.63) and 3.29 (SD 0.50) liters respectively. All these differences were statistically significant (p=0.000). Similarly the mean of FEV₁/FVC in male and female was 79% (SD 10) and 75% (SD 3) respectively and this difference was also statistically significant (p=0.024)

Similar studies were done to see the difference of PFT values in male and female diabetic patients. In a study by Fuso et al [16] in 2012 on multiple regression analysis identified male sex (beta coefficient = 0.423, p = 0.004) were independent correlates of MVV. Copenhagen City Heart study by P Lange et al in 2002 showed that in both sexes, nondiabetic individuals had a higher level of both FEV₁ and FVC % predicted values, whereas those with diabetes had the lowest values. For the diabetic group, the reduction in both FEV₁ and FVC was substantial, ranging 8% of that predicted. The unadjusted decline in lung function i.e both FEV₁ and FVC in mL/yr according to the three diabetes groups i.e normal, diabetes and new diabetes group was higher in males than in females. This finding is opposite to our finding as we found lower lung function values in females compared to males. Though Fuso et al on doing multiple linear regression analyses of FEV₁ and FVC decline in females and males with regard to diabetes, no significant association between FEV₁ and FVC decline and diabetes category was observed. Since gender is an independent predictor of lung function so though in our study we find significant difference in lung function in male and female but we need to do a regression analysis to get a true picture.

Conclusion

This study showed the relationship between type 2 diabetes mellitus and its affect on PFT. The PFT parameters i.e FVC, FEV₁ and TLC all decreased with increased blood sugar level and with poor diabetes control. Duration of diabetes also had a negative effect in PFT parameters. Female gender had lower values compared to male and even obese study subject had lower PFT values compared to study subject with normal BMI. As in diabetes there may be a affect of inflammatory markers that may lead to damage to respiratory tract and may lead to decrease in PFT values so strict control of

blood sugar level in diabetes may retard the progression of falling PFT values.

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